

IMPACT OF MANAGEMENT AND MARKETING PRACTICES ON SERVICE EFFECTIVENESS IN NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS: A QUANTITATIVE STUDY OF LIBRARIES.

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Abstract

This study examines the effectiveness of non-profit organizations. Libraries are taken as a special case to find out the role of management practices and marketing practices in improving service effectiveness. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire from library users and staff members. 209 valid responses were collected and analyzed through SPSS. Descriptive statistics and reliability analysis were used to assess the quality of data. Correlational and multiple regression analyses were used to examine relationships among the study variables.

Finding revealed strong and positive relationships between management practices, marketing practices, and service effectiveness. Regression results indicate that management and marketing practices jointly explain a substantial proportion of variance in service effectiveness ($R^2=0.639$). Both practices were found to be statistically significant predictors of service effectiveness, with management practices demonstrating a stronger influence. Diagnostic tests have confirmed that the regression model was statistically appropriate and free from multicollinearity issues.

The study concludes that effective management and strategic marketing practices are essential for enhancing the service effectiveness in non-profit organization. Using libraries as a case study, the results indicate that strong internal management processes and effective external communication strategies are necessary to improve service delivery and user engagement.

INTRODUCTION

CHAPTER 1

Background of the Study

Organizations that are not for-profit are established for the development of society and are just as important as for-profit organizations. These organizations are necessary for providing services that improve education, enhance welfare services, and foster a better community. In comparison to the profit-driven organizations, NPOs have completely

different goals. NPOs aim to achieve social objectives instead of monetary benefits (Anheier 2014). Despite understanding the importance of NPOs for society, several organizations face severe challenges in achieving their goals. NPOs face difficulties in continuing their operations, engaging stakeholders, and providing quality services due to ineffective management and limited marketing practices. (Werke and Bogale 2024).

Especially in Pakistan, service-based institutions like libraries are apparently struggling. Libraries are one of the most important NPOs that cater to the public's educational requirements, but unfortunately, lack skilled managers and organized marketing practices. When such professional approaches of the organization are lacking, the organization limits its efficiency, and the visibility is also compromised in the long run.

Therefore, the purpose of the research is to find out how management and marketing are not only suitable for profitable businesses but are equally important for non-profit organizations to achieve their goals and objectives.

Even though the NPOs are essential to develop a community, Organizations overlook the importance of effective management and effective marketing practices, believing that effective management and marketing are only necessary for-profit organizations. Consequently, Libraries and other organization's engagement is decreasing day by day, operations are limited and sources are not utilized properly (Gehring 2024). The research objective is to fulfill the identified gap by identifying how effective management and marketing techniques can enhance the services of libraries and help to increase the visibility of the NPOs including libraries.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact of management and marketing strategies on the performance of the NPOs. We consider "libraries of Pakistan" as a special case to complete our study.

This research will highlight the importance of management and marketing practices for the service effectiveness of Pakistan's non-profit sector. It emphasizes how effective management and marketing practices can enhance the development of the community, functional effectiveness and sustainability. By focusing on libraries, the research will present the actionable issues faced by the users and society.

This study broadly focuses on the non-profit sector, the collection of data and empirical analysis are purely from the libraries of Pakistan. Libraries provide community-centered services without any profit motive, that's why we have chosen libraries as an exemplary case. The results of this study can be implemented in other similar service-oriented NPOs.

Research Questions

1. The research examines why Non-Profit Organizations overlook effective management and marketing practices.
2. The research aims to find out how the management strategies contribute to improving the effectiveness of NPOs.
3. The research aims to find out how the marketing practices will increase the visibility and interaction of the NPOs.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Management and marketing play a key role in achieving success within organizations. The corporate sector understands the importance of management and marketing, whereas the non-profit organizations do not afford them the same level of attention. Studies have highlighted that effective management and marketing are equally necessary for non-profit organizations, as they facilitate the organization in achieving its goals and objectives and enhance its visibility and communication with society (Ada, Altin et al. 2022, Gehring 2024).

Management in Non-Profit Organizations

Management is the process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling resources to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization. Drucker (1990) defines management as "the process of making human strengths productive and weaknesses irrelevant." Effective management leverages structure, accountability and direction, which results in improved performance outcomes (Heinrich 2002). Sargeant (2014) states that non-profit organization management includes the challenge of reconciling mission-driven goals with operational realities. If there is no proper management system, non-profits face difficulties utilizing resources, measuring performance and sustaining programs (Sargeant and Shang 2010)

Leadership and Strategic Planning

Leadership plays a key role in inspiring employees and cultivating Goal-oriented cultures. Effective leadership promotes motivation and cooperation, due to which service effectiveness is enhanced within the non-profit organizations. Bryson (2018) stated

that strategic planning helps to align resources with the goals and objectives of the organization. It also helps the organization to evolve the environment (Bryson 2018).

In Pakistan, several non-profits, including libraries, lack effective leadership structures. First of all, organizations including libraries, do not feel the need of trained managers and effective management. If they feel so, the administrators and librarians are placed at managerial posts without formal training, which results in poor service effectiveness, lack of innovation and accountability (Mahmood 2014).

Marketing in Non-Profit Organizations

Marketing for NPOs focuses on enhancing communication, promoting services and conveying value to stakeholders. Unlike For-profit organizations, NPOs approach things differently; instead of financial gain, it targets connection building and mission alignment (Kazanskaia 2025). Kotler and Andreasen (2008) stated Non-Profit Marketing as “the design and implementation of programs aimed at influencing the acceptability of social ideas and services.” The objective is to create awareness, enhance visibility and encourage engagement (Kazanskaia 2025).

Marketing Strategies

NPOs operate in a competitive environment and are characterized by limited resources, growing stakeholder expectations and strict accountability. In this environment, marketing strategies are becoming increasingly vital for NPOs. Previous research suggests that strategic marketing empowers non-profits to effectively communicate their goals and enhance communication with donors, beneficiaries and society (Werke and Bogale 2024).

NPOs have limited resources, due to which the organizations have to choose cost-effective strategies. Digital marketing tools such as email campaigns, online storytelling and social media have emerged as cost-effective strategies that allow non-profit organizations to enhance visibility and foster meaningful communication (Kazanskaia 2025).

Relationship between Management, Marketing, and Organizational Effectiveness

Effective management and marketing are closely linked to the service effectiveness of the NPOs, both

play a crucial role in the achievement of goals and objectives. Previous research highlights that effective management such as planning, proper allocation of resources, strong leadership and a trustworthy engagement with stakeholders, helps the organization to implement successful marketing strategies (Sultan and Ahmed 2024). Marketing works as a bridge between the organization and its target audience by communicating the services provided by the organization. Marketing describes why the services are necessary and how helpful the services are, so the audience easily understands the value of the services. Effective marketing enhances credibility, visibility and builds trust (Werke and Bogale 2024). Studies indicate that effective managerial leadership and marketing practices not only enhance communication with stakeholders but also strengthen the organizational responsiveness and performance (Kazanskaia 2025). Effective management and marketing practices contribute meaningfully to the organizational performance. These practices enhance public awareness, utilize resources effectively and improve the organization’s reputation. Both management and marketing are necessary components that drive organizational success in dynamic environments.

The Pakistani Non-Profit Context

In Pakistan, Many non-profit organizations, including libraries, operate on very low budgets. Technical and managerial skills are also limited. Studies indicate that ineffective administrative systems and inadequate public relations result in unsatisfactory performance. Libraries in Pakistan are struggling with low participation and outdated infrastructure, which has contributed to a decline in reading culture and limited visibility, indicating a need for more effective management and strategic marketing practices to boost public engagement (Rasheed 2025). Studies on library services show that marketing tools like social media are cost-effective and easy to operate but unfortunately, due to lack of managerial skills, Pakistani non-profit organizations are unable to utilize these advanced technologies and strategies (Malik and Bashir 2023).

Conceptual Model of Study

Research presents a conceptual framework that explores how management strategies and marketing

practices impact the effectiveness of NPOs with libraries in Pakistan, serving as the primary examples. The framework is based on existing literature that elaborates that internal systems, such as strategic planning and leadership, contribute to organizational efficiency, whereas external communication strategies enhance public trust, visibility and engagement with stakeholders (Bryson 2018).

Studies suggest that the combination of effective management and strategic marketing leads to a synergy that enhances services, fosters community loyalty, and boosts organizational performance (Sargeant and Shang 2010). In Pakistan, ineffective leadership practices and a lack of investment in

marketing have limited libraries capacity to attract users and maintain sustainable operations. Consequently, improving these functional areas will give us better results for community-focused non-profits (Bryson 2018) (Kazanskaia 2025).

Research Variables

- **Independent Variables**
 - Management Practices
 - Marketing Practices
- **Dependent Variables**
 - Organizational Effectiveness

MODEL DESCRIPTION

1. Management Practices

Management practices include planning, organizing, leadership, controlling functions, and human resources framework. Effective management structures enhance accountability, performance evaluation, decision-making processes and service effectiveness.

2. Marketing Practices

Marketing practices involve promotional initiatives, communication strategies, stakeholder engagement and relationship development. Effective marketing practices enhance visibility, foster trust and credibility, and encourage public interaction.

3. Organizational Effectiveness

This leads to the quality of services, operational effectiveness, public engagement and the achievement of the goals and objectives.

Theoretical Connection

Management and marketing practices have a direct positive impact on an organization’s effectiveness. The assumption is that when institutions such as libraries implement management practices and proactive communication strategies, they result in increased community involvement, enhanced service results and improved institutional sustainability.

This framework will present the research methodology, selection of variables, formulation of the hypothesis and analyses in the upcoming chapters.

Summary

This Study indicates that management and marketing are necessary instruments for enhancing the effectiveness of non-profit organizations. Without these strategies, organizations may experience inefficiency, inadequate communication and decreasing significance. In Pakistan, where the

majority of non-profits function without structured management or promotional methods, the incorporation of these strategies could significantly improve service quality and engagement with the community.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter describes the methods used to carry out the study. It covers the research design, the population and sample, the instruments for data collection, and the techniques for data analysis. Given that the study focuses solely on two to three non-profit libraries, the methodology is tailored to be small-scale, practical and exploratory.

Research Design

This research has a quantitative research design using a descriptive correlational approach. The design allows for the assessment of connections among variables and facilitates hypothesis testing using statistical methods.

Population and Sample

Research is based on non-profit organizations, we have targeted the libraries as a representative example due to constraints in time, accessibility, and practicality.

A convenience sample of two to three libraries was selected. Participants included are library professionals and users. A sample size of 100-120 respondents was taken. 30 to 50 users are selected per library. The sample size is perfect for a small exploratory research project.

Data Collection Methods

Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire aimed at quantitatively assessing the influence of management and marketing practices on the effectiveness of organizations in libraries functioning as non-profit entities in Pakistan. The tool was created in accordance with the study's aims and theoretical framework.

The questionnaire was divided into five sections.

Section A collected demographic and contextual information such as the respondent's category,

library name (as an open-ended response), job title, experience, qualifications, and user category.

Section B examined library usage trends, the services accessed, satisfaction levels with library offerings, and staff responsiveness, using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (1) to Strongly Disagree (5).

Section C assessed respondents' views on management practices (encompassing leadership, planning, supervision, and decision-making) and marketing practices and their combined impact on management of service quality, visibility, user satisfaction, and overall organizational effectiveness, employing a 5-point Likert scale (from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree).

Section D featured open-ended questions designed to gather recommendations for enhancing management, marketing, and service effectiveness.

The questionnaire was crafted to ensure consistency, clarity, and appropriateness for statistical analysis while directly aiding in the evaluation of the study's conceptual model.

Data Collection Procedure

Questionnaires were distributed to the staff members and users with their consent. Responses were gathered from 3 libraries within a time frame of 15 days.

Data Analysis

Because of the limited sample size, the analysis is primarily descriptive rather than statistical. Quantitative data is presented in tables, along with percentages and average scores. The results are interpreted in the context of existing literature, facilitating an assessment of management and marketing enhance service effectiveness.

Summary

This Chapter outlined the methodological approach for the research. It provides reasons for employing the quantitative method, utilizing a small sample, applying convenience sampling, and conducting descriptive analysis appropriate for exploratory investigations into non-profit libraries.

**CHAPTER 4
DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS**

Introduction

The chapter presents the statistical analysis and interpretation of data collected to determine the role of management practices and marketing practices in enhancing service effectiveness in non-profit academic libraries. Data is analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics and results described using descriptive statistics, reliability analysis and correlation analysis.

Response Rate and Data Screening

A total of 200+ respondents were targeted for data collection using a mix-mode survey approach. An online questionnaire was created using Google Forms by which 101 responses were received. In addition to that 120 hard form questionnaire were distributed manually out of which 112 completed questionnaires were returned.

A total of 213 questionnaires were collected from both methods. 04 questionnaires were excluded due to inconsistency. 209 questionnaires were retained for the final analysis.

Statistics

	Respondent Category	Name of Library	Designation	Years of Experience	Highest Qualification	Category of user	Frequency of Visit	Propose of using library
N Valid	205	209	21	57	98	209	209	209
Missing	4	0	188	152	111	0	0	0

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics.

Respondent Category

Results show that most of the respondents were library users (85.9%) while 14.1 % were library staff.

It shows that the user perceptions highlight the data which is appropriate given the study's focus on service effectiveness.

Respondent Category

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Library Staff	29	13.9	14.1	14.1
	Library User	176	84.2	85.9	100.0
	Total	205	98.1	100.0	
Missing	System	4	1.9		
Total		209	100.0		

Name of Libraries

Ensuring the institutional confidentiality and encourage unbiased responses. The names of Participating libraries were not disclosed. Names of libraries are replaced by the neutral identifiers. This approach is consistent with ethical guidelines in

social sciences research and does not affect the validity and reliability of the results.

The majority of respondents belonged to Library B (43.1%), followed by Library A (33.5%) and other libraries are at last termed as Library C (23.4%).

Name of Library

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Library A	70	33.5	33.5	33.5
	Library B	90	43.1	43.1	76.6
	Library C	49	23.4	23.4	100.0
	Total	209	100.0	100.0	

The distribution ensures representation from multiple institutional contexts.

Designation and Years of Experience

Assistant Librarians constituted the largest group among the staff respondents with the percentage of 87.5%, followed by the librarians and clerical staff. Most Staff respondents had more than one year experience. This data indicated the involvement of experienced professionals.

Designation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Librarian	1	.5	4.2	4.2
	Assistant Librarian	21	10.0	87.5	91.7
	Clerk / Assistant	2	1.0	8.3	100.0
	Total	24	11.5	100.0	
Missing	System	185	88.5		
Total		209	100.0		

Highest Qualification

Most respondents are qualifying bachelor’s degree whereas the percentage of respondent is 62.2. Followed by the master’s degree with the percentage

of 25.5. This data reflects adequately educated respondent was involved to provide informed responses.

Highest Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Intermediate	4	1.9	4.1	4.1
	Bachelors	61	29.2	62.2	66.3
	M.Sc/Mlis	25	12.0	25.5	91.8
	Masters of Philosophy	8	3.8	8.2	100.0
	Total	98	46.9	100.0	
Missing	System	111	53.1		
Total		209	100.0		

Category of Users

The majority of the respondents were students, accounting for 84.2%. Which indicates that the students contribute as the primary user group of the libraries. This is followed by library staff who

represented 9.6%. A smaller portion of respondents belong to other categories including researchers 1.9% whereas teachers and members of the general public each accounted for less than 2.4%.

Category of user

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	176	84.2	84.2	84.2
	Teacher	4	1.9	1.9	86.1
	General Public	5	2.4	2.4	88.5
	Researcher	4	1.9	1.9	90.4
	Library staff	20	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	209	100.0	100.0	

Frequency of Library Visit

The findings highlight that more than half of the respondents were daily users comprising 50.7% of the valid responses. The results indicates a high level of regular engagement of the respondents with the libraries. Whereas weekly, monthly and occasional

occurrences are accounted for at 19.6%, 9.1%, 20.6% respectively. A high percentage of regular and weekly users indicate substantial exposure to library services, thereby enhancing the reliability of their responses regarding service effectiveness.

Frequency of Visit

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Daily	106	50.7	50.7	50.7
	Weekly	41	19.6	19.6	70.3

Monthly	19	9.1	9.1	79.4
Occasionally	43	20.6	20.6	100.0
Total	209	100.0	100.0	

4.3.7 Purpose of Using the Library

Most of the respondents declared reading and studying as the primary reason for visiting the library, reported by 76.1% of valid respondents. It indicates that the main role of libraries is to provide updated

reading resources and an environment. Other purposes, although less frequent but reflect the multifunctional nature of library usage, including research-related and informational needs.

Propose of using library

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Reading/Study	159	76.1	76.1	76.1
	Borrowing Books	9	4.3	4.3	80.4
	Research Work	29	13.9	13.9	94.3
	Internet/Facilities	4	1.9	1.9	96.2
	Working	8	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total	209	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Analysis of Current Library Service Effectiveness

This section presents a descriptive analysis of respondent’s perceptions regarding the current effectiveness of library services. Analyses are taken from SPSS output and based on frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations. The idea was to examine the present condition of library

services and highlight the areas requiring improvement.

Access to Library Updates and User Connectivity

To find out how effectively libraries remain connected with their users, respondents were asked whether they regularly receive updates about the services, activities or resources of the library or not.

Access to Library Updates

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	May Be	29	13.9	14.1	14.1
	No	76	36.4	37.1	51.2
	Yes	100	47.8	48.8	100.0
	Total	205	98.1	100.0	
Missing	System	4	1.9		
Total		209	100.0		

Results highlight that only 48.8% respondents are receiving regular updates from libraries, which is even less than half. Whereas a substantial proportion of 37.1% respondents stated that they do not receive any updates. The result indicates a weak communication link between libraries and their users.

Libraries, even working as non-profit organizations, play a key role in building an educated society. Therefore, libraries need to strengthen their information dissemination and communication channels to ensure consistent engagement with the users. Libraries can enhance their connection with the users by using several low-cost and free methods

of interaction like notice boards, email alerts and SMS notifications. Whereas, Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and X are cost-effective and user-friendly tools for building a healthy and long-lasting relationship with users.

User’s Perception of Current Library Service Effectiveness

Users are also asked to rate their experience of various aspects such as availability of resources, staff responses, environment, and overall satisfaction using a 5-Point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Satisfaction with library services	205	1	5	3.85	.951
Behaviour of Staff	205	1	5	3.74	1.083
Working of library	205	1	5	3.83	1.030
Rules of library	205	1	5	3.82	.938
Response of staff	201	1	5	3.70	.970
Valid N (listwise)	201				

Interpretation and Discussion

Results indicate that the users perceive the current effectiveness of library services as moderate. **Overall satisfaction with library services** resulted in a mean value of **3.85**. It highlights that there is scope for improvement in services, although the values are satisfactory. The **working of the library** and **clarity of the library rules** also resulted in favorable mean values of **3.83, 3.82 respectively**. Whereas, there is also scope for enhancement.

However, the results have described comparatively lower mean values for **the behavior of staff (Mean = 3.74)** and **response of staff (Mean = 3.70)**. The results indicate that while the performance of staff is adequate but it does not meet the user’s expectations strongly. Higher standard deviations for these items indicate variability in user experiences, highlighting inconsistencies in service delivery.

Results highlight that there is room for improvement in all aspects. Whereas, special attention is required particularly for staff responsiveness and behavior, as these dimensions are valued lowest among all service indicators.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis was taken to determine the internal consistency of the measurement scales. Cronbach’s alpha was used as the reliability coefficient, as it is widely accepted in social science research.

Individual Construct Reliability

In the first phase, the reliability of each variable was checked separately to ensure internal consistency.

Management Practices

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.769	5

Marketing Practices

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.725	3

Service Effectiveness

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.761	3

All values exceed the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating satisfactory reliability.

Combined Reliability of Core Study Variables

Since the study examines the impact of management and marketing practices on service effectiveness, a combined reliability analysis was also conducted by merging all variables. Results are presented below:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.879	11

The combined Cronbach’s alpha value of **0.879** has shown **excellent internal consistency**.

Descriptive Analysis of Main Study Variables.

This section presents descriptive analysis of the main variables of the study, namely **management practices, marketing practices, and service effectiveness**. Variables were measured using Likert

Scale of five point ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree.

Descriptive Analysis of Management Practices

Management practices were assessed using five questions that focused on managerial effectiveness, professionalism, and administrative support.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Effective management improves services	209	3	5	4.44	.706
Managers to manage the library	209	2	5	4.26	.747
Effective management reduces problems	208	2	5	4.42	.744
Management professionals increase service effectiveness.	208	1	5	4.09	.888
Lack of management has negative impact	209	1	5	4.22	.904
Valid N (listwise)	207				

The results shows high level of agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of management practices in libraries. The range of management-related questions is from 4.09 to 4.44, indicating positive perceptions of effective managerial practices, problem-solving ability and the positive role of management in effective service delivery.

Descriptive Analysis of Marketing Practice

Marketing practices are assessed using three questions that focus on visibility, connectivity and awareness/unawareness of available resources.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Marketing activities increase library usage	209	1	5	4.14	.919
Effective marketing helps users	205	2	5	4.30	.703
Lack of marketing makes people unaware	209	3	5	4.25	.641
Valid N (listwise)	205				

Marketing practices also received favorable evaluations from respondents. The mean scores ranged from 4.14 to 4.30, indicating agreement that marketing activities help users, increase awareness, and promote library usage. These findings highlight the perceived importance of marketing efforts in enhancing library visibility and user engagement.

Descriptive Analysis of Service Effectiveness

The impact of management and marketing practices on service effectiveness is assessed through three questions.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Management and marketing are equally important	209	2	5	4.31	.695
Libraries need proper management and marketing	205	3	5	4.35	.696
Management and marketing impact	206	3	5	4.42	.633
Valid N (listwise)	202				

Service effectiveness items demonstrated strong positive responses, with mean values ranging from 4.31 to 4.42. Respondents generally agreed that library services are effective in meeting user needs and that both management and marketing practices contribute to improved service outcomes. The standard deviation values indicate a stable response pattern across participants.

management practices, marketing practices, and service effectiveness in libraries. The consistently high mean values and acceptable variability support the inclusion of these variables in subsequent correlation and regression analyses to examine their relationships and impact.

Overall Summary

Overall, the descriptive analysis shows that respondents hold positive perceptions of

Correlational Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the nature and strength of relationships between the variables. Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used

to measure the data on a Likert scale and to meet the assumptions required for parametric testing. Composite mean scores were created for

management practices, marketing practices, and service effectiveness, and correlation analysis was performed using SPSS.

Correlation Matrix of Core Study Variables

Correlations

		MGMT_PR	MKT_PR	SER_EFFC
MGMT_PR	Pearson Correlation	1	.716**	.754**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	209	209	209
MKT_PR	Pearson Correlation	.716**	1	.726**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	209	209	209
SER_EFFC	Pearson Correlation	.754**	.726**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	209	209	209

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results shows a significantly strong and positive relationship between management practices and marketing practices ($r = .716, p < .01$). This indicates that libraries with effective management practices also tend to implement stronger marketing practices. A strong positive correlation was also seen between management practices and service effectiveness ($r = .754, p < .01$). This indicates that improvements in management practices are strongly associated with higher levels of perceived service effectiveness in libraries.

Similarly, marketing practices were positively and significantly related to service effectiveness ($r = .726, p < .01$), indicating that effective marketing activities contribute substantially to improved library service effectiveness and visibility.

Overall, the correlation results confirm that both management practices and marketing practices are closely linked with service effectiveness, supporting the study’s conceptual framework and justifying further regression analysis to examine predictive relationships.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model Summary describes the strong relation of independent variable and dependent variable. The value of $R=.800$ presents a high overall correlation between the IVs and DV. The R^2 value of .639 indicates that 63.9% of the variance in library service effectiveness is explained by management and marketing practices. The adjusted R^2 (.636) assures the stability of the model as the number of the predictors are adjusted.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			Sig. Change	F	
				R Square Change	F Change	df1			df2
1	.800 ^a	.639	.636	.34016	.639	182.485	2	206	.000

Predictors: (Constant), MKT_PR, MGMT_PR

ANOVA Results

ANOVA results are showing that the regression model is statistically significant ($F = 182.485, P < .001$). This shows that the model is reliable and predicts library service effectiveness and that the combined effect of management and marketing practices is meaningful.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	42.231	2	21.116	182.485	.000 ^b
	Residual	23.837	206	.116		
	Total	66.068	208			

a. Dependent Variable: SER_EFFC

b. Predictors: (Constant), MKT_PR, MGMT_PR

Regression Coefficients

Regression coefficients reveal that both predictors have a significantly positive influence on library service effectiveness. Management practices (**MGMT_PR**) have a significantly positive impact on service effectiveness ($P=.480, p<.001$). If one unit in management practices increases, service effectiveness also increases by **0.469 units**. Marketing practices (**MKT_PR**) have a significantly positive impact on service effectiveness ($P=.382, p<.001$). If one unit in marketing practices increases, service effectiveness also increases by **0.351 units**.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.850	.185		4.598	.000		
	MGMT_PR	.469	.059	.480	8.009	.000	.488	2.050
	MKT_PR	.351	.055	.382	6.382	.000	.488	2.050

a. Dependent Variable: SER_EFFC

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions		
				(Constant)	MGMT_PR	MKT_PR
1	1	2.984	1.000	.00	.00	.00

2	.011	16.409	.96	.07	.23
3	.005	23.628	.04	.93	.77

a. Dependent Variable: SER_EFFC

Residual Analysis

Residual statistics indicate that the model fits the data remarkably. The sample size of 209 observations is sufficient for the analysis. The standardized residuals largely fall within the acceptable range of ± 3 , with only one observation exceeding this threshold. It indicates that the presence of outliers is minimal and do not affect the results significantly.

Summary

Overall, the complete regression analysis shows that both management and marketing practices have a significantly positive impact on service effectiveness of libraries.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis

After conducting regression analysis to find out the impact of management practices and marketing practices on service effectiveness, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using AMOS was performed to further validate the model and assess overall model fit, structural relationships, and explanatory power.

Final Structural Model

The figure illustrates the relationships between management practices, marketing practices, and service effectiveness, including standardized path coefficients and measurement indicators.

Model Fit Assessment

The structural model was evaluated using multiple goodness-of-fit indices to determine how well the proposed model fits the observed data.

The findings are

- CMIN/DF = 2.853
- CFI = 0.926
- IFI = 0.928
- TLI = 0.881

Overall, the fit indices indicate that the structural model provides an adequate representation of the data.

Structural Path Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The structural paths were examined to test the proposed hypotheses. The results shows that management practices significantly and positively affect service effectiveness ($p=.046$). Where the marketing practices also impact positive on service effectiveness ($p.018$).

The results indicate that the marketing practices ($P = 0.512$) have a slightly stronger relative influence compared to management practices ($P = 0.495$).

This proves that both HYPOTHESES are supported.

Explanatory Power of the Model

The squared multiple Correlation (R^2) for service effectiveness is 0.965. It indicates that 96.5% of the variance in service effectiveness is explained by management and marketing practices, it highlights the strong explanatory power of the model.

Such a high R^2 confirms that the proposed framework effectively captures the major determinants of service effectiveness.

Total Effects and Indicator Strength

The total effect analysis shows:

- A one-unit increase in management practices lead to a 1.619-unit increase in service effectiveness.
- A one-unit increase in marketing practices leads to a 0.765-unit increase in service effectiveness. Furthermore the strongest indicators within the model were:
- Mgmt5 ($R^2 = 0.657$) - Strongest management indicator

- Mkt2 ($R^2 = 0.586$) - Strongest marketing indicator
- SE1 ($R^2 = 0.694$) - Strongest service effectiveness indicator

These results confirm that the measurement and structural components of the model are both statistically strong and reliable.

Summary of SEM Findings

Overall, the SEM analysis confirms that the structural model fits the data well and that both management and marketing practices significantly enhance service effectiveness. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power and validates the proposed theoretical framework.

Chapter 5**DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION**

This research examined the impact of **management and marketing practices** on library service effectiveness. These findings are clear that both practices have a significantly positive impact on service effectiveness.

Correlational results indicate a significantly strong positive relation among all variables. Whereas, regression results indicate that effective management and marketing practices together explain a large proportion of variation in service effectiveness ($R^2 = 0.639$). Between these two, management practices have a stronger influence, indicating that effective leadership, planning, and coordination are necessary to improve the services of NPOs. On the other hand, Marketing practices also have a significantly positive effect to improve the visibility and services of the NPOs. The results highlights the importance of communication and user engagement in enhancing service perception and visibility. The diagnostic test indicates that the regression model is stable and free from multicollinearity issues.

Conclusion

The research proves that effective management and marketing practices are key drivers of Non-Profit Organization service effectiveness. Strong management systems provide the foundation for quality service delivery, while marketing practices not only enhance the visibility of the organization but also enhance the user awareness and engagement.

NPOs including libraries that aim to improve service effectiveness, visibility and user engagement, should focus on strengthening both internal management processes and external marketing and communication strategies.

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